

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL FOR

Assessing the electrochemical performance of different phenazines as cathode for Zn-ion battery

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Table S1 Overview of chemical structures, molecular weights (MW), and theoretical specific capacities (C_{theor}) of phenazine and its derivatives

Chemical structure	Name (abbreviation)	MW / g mol ⁻¹	C_{theor}^* / mA h g ⁻¹
	Phenazine (PZ)	180.21	297.45
	Phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA)	224.21	239.07
	Phenazin-1-ol or 1-Hydroxyphenazine (POH)	196.20	273.20
	Phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN)	223.23	240.12

* Theoretical specific capacitance calculated at a fully discharged state:

$C_{\text{theor}} = \frac{nF}{3.6MW}$, where n is the number of electrons (2), F the Faraday constant (96485 C mol⁻¹), and 3.6 the conversion from seconds to hour.

Text S1 Biological production and purification of PCA

PCA production was carried out using recombinant cells of *Escherichia coli*. Competent *E. coli* QH4 cells were transformed via heat shock with the plasmid pE-PCA [1], which carries all the genes of the *phzABCDEFG* operon from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* for the conversion of chorismate into PCA. Transformed cells were grown overnight in 5 mL of Lennox Broth medium containing 10 g L⁻¹ tryptone, 5 g L⁻¹ yeast extract, and 5 g L⁻¹ NaCl, supplemented with 80 µg mL⁻¹ ampicillin, at 37 °C and 225 rpm. Subsequently, 1 mL of the overnight culture was inoculated into 50 mL of TB medium containing 12 g L⁻¹ tryptone, 24 g L⁻¹ yeast extract, 0.17 mol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, and 0.72 mol L⁻¹ K₂HPO₄, supplemented with 2% (w/w) glycerol and 80 µg L⁻¹ ampicillin. Cultures were incubated at 30 °C and 225 rpm. Once the optical density at 600 nm reached 0.8–1.0, PCA production was induced by the addition of 1 mmol L⁻¹ IPTG, and cells were incubated for an additional 33 h.

PCA purification was performed as described previously [2]. First, cells were separated from the culture supernatant by centrifugation at 4000 × g for 30 min. The cell-free supernatant was acidified to pH 2.5 using 5 mol L⁻¹ HCl. PCA was then extracted using one-fifth volume of chloroform. The organic phase was recovered and back-extracted with four volumes of 0.01 mol L⁻¹ NaOH. The resulting aqueous phase was acidified to pH 2 with HCl and extracted again with one-fifth volume of chloroform. The organic phase was collected and evaporated using a rotary evaporator to obtain purified PCA.

Text S2

The ^1H Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (HNMR) of phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), phenazin-1-ol (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN) can be seen in Fig. S1, along with a comparison between the standard and biologically synthesized PCA. All obtained peaks for PZ*, POH [3], PCA[3] and PCN [4,5] agree with literature. Previously, samples were dissolved in CDCl_3 and analyzed using a Bruker Advance III-600 equipment, operating at 14.1 T magnetic field (600 MHz for ^1H).

*<https://sdfs.db.aist.go.jp/> - accessed 2/26/2025

a)

b)

Fig. S1 ^1H NMR of the compounds used during the electrochemical tests: **a)** phenazine, **b)** phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), **c)** phenazine-1-ol, **d)** phenazine-1-carboxamide, and **e)** comparison between the standard and biologically synthesized PCA.

c)

d)

Fig. S1 (*continuation*) ¹H NMR of the compounds used during the electrochemical tests: **a)** phenazine, **b)** phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), **c)** phenazine-1-ol, **d)** phenazine-1-carboxamide, and **e)** comparison between the standard and biologically synthesized PCA.

e)

Fig. S1 (*continuation*) ¹H NMR of the compounds used during the electrochemical tests: **a**) phenazine, **b**) phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), **c**) phenazin-1-ol, **d**) phenazine-1-carboxamide, and **e**) comparison between the standard and biologically synthesized PCA.

a)

b)

Fig. S2 a) Cyclic voltammetry (2^{nd} scan at 0.1 mV s^{-1}) of electrodes using PZ as the active material for distinct carbon black materials as additive to increase conductivity and **b)** specific capacity (C) as a function of the number of cycles during charge and discharge experiments using distinct mass current densities (refer to the numbers in green in the inset, which are measured in mA g^{-1}). Flexible graphite was used as current collector. Experimental conditions: A Zn foil was used as the anode and $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ served as the electrolyte. The arrows indicate the scan direction.

Fig. S3 Specific capacity of the discharging cycle (C) as a function of the number of cycles in galvanostatic charge and discharge measurements over prolonged tests (1000 cycles) at a current density of 1 A g^{-1} . For each carbon current collector, two different experiments were carried out, with colors indicating the different materials used as current collector. Experimental conditions: A Zn foil was used as the anode and $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ served as the electrolyte.

Fig. S4 Evolution of cell potential (E) as a function of specific capacity (C) during galvanostatic charge and discharge measurements using distinct current densities and distinct materials (see inset): phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), 1-hydroxiphenazine (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN). Experimental conditions: A Zn foil was used as the anode and $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ served as the electrolyte.

Fig. S5 *Ex situ* ¹H NMR spectra of the phenazine (PZ) compound after use as the active material in the cathode of a Zn-ion battery under different conditions: pristine, after the charge step (1.4 V), and after the discharge step (0.75, 0.55, and 0.3 V). Experimental conditions: the working electrode was prepared with PZ (65% *m/m*), KCB (20% *m/m*), and PVDF solution in NMP (15% *m/m*) using 2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ as electrolyte.

Fig. S6 Evolution of cell potential (E vs. Zn/Zn^{2+}) as a function of time (t) for the shelf tests and using electrochemical devices assembled with different active materials: phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), 1-hydroxiphenazine (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN). The solid lines represent the charging (on the left) and discharging (on the right) step carried out at 800 mA g^{-1} . The dashed line represents the open circuit potential (OCP) measurement and the arrows indicate the potential drop after the charging step. Experimental conditions: A Zn foil was used as the anode and $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ served as the electrolyte.

Fig. S7 Average specific energy density ($E_s / \text{Wh kg}^{-1}$) and average specific power density ($P_s / \text{W kg}^{-1}$) for the different active materials assessed in this work (phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), 1-hydroxiphenazine (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN)) using $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ and $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ as supporting electrolyte and for some selected papers (see references [6–10]).

a)

b)

Fig. S8 a) Complex plane and **b)** bode plot of active materials. Experimental conditions: A Zn foil and Ag/AgCl/ 3 mol L⁻¹ was used as the anode and reference electrode, respectively, and 2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ served as the electrolyte. Phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), phenazine-1-ol (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN).

a)

b)

Fig. S9 Electrochemical diffusion coefficient (\tilde{D}) as a function of the fraction of Zn^{2+} (and/or H^+) ions incorporated in the active material (x) for different **a)** active materials and **b)** PZ using distinct carbon materials (see inset for details). The electrochemical tests for determination of \tilde{D} were conducted at 400 mA g^{-1} . Experimental conditions: A Zn foil was used as the anode and $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ served as the electrolyte. Phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), phenazine-1-ol (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN).

Fig. S10 Discharge step profile of a galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) experiment (400 mA g^{-1} for 60 s, followed by a period (100 s) without current application) for the distinct organic compounds. Experimental conditions: A Zn foil was used as the anode and $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ served as the electrolyte. Phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), phenazine-1-ol (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN).

Fig. S11 Cyclic voltammograms (2nd cycle at 0.1 mV s^{-1}) of electrodes containing **a)** phenazine (PZ), **b)** phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), **c)** 1-hydroxyphenazine (POH), and **d)** phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN) under distinct pH conditions (see inset). Experimental conditions: A Zn foil was used as the anode and $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ ZnSO}_4$ served as the electrolyte. The electrolyte was acidified with 0.5 mol L^{-1} of H_2SO_4 . The arrows indicate the scan direction.

Fig. S12 Scanning electron micrographs of electrode materials containing phenazine (as active material), KCB and PVDF at distinct conditions: as prepared and after the charge (1.4 vs. Zn/Zn²⁺) and discharge steps (0.3 vs. Zn/Zn²⁺) using 2 mol L⁻¹ Zn(OTf)₂ and 1 mol L⁻¹ Zn(OTf)₂ dissolved in 50 g L⁻¹ Polyvinylalcohol as electrolytes (see inset for details). Separate electrodes were prepared for each half cycle and using a Zn foil as anode.

Table S2 Mass and atomic percentages of elements obtained from EDS analyses of the micrographs shown in Fig. S12

Element	As prepared		2 mol L ⁻¹ Zn(OTf) ₂				1 mol L ⁻¹ Zn(OTf) ₂ + 50 g L ⁻¹ PVA			
			After discharge		After charge		After discharge		After charge	
	wt%	at%	wt%	at%	wt%	at%	wt%	at%	wt%	at%
C	88.83	92.23	26.63	42.04	37.34	53.04	49.56	64.55	68.89	79.3
N	0.00	0.00	0.74	1.00	1.55	1.89	1.32	1.47	0.56	0.56
O	5.21	4.06	22.22	26.33	17.38	18.53	17.43	17.04	12.81	11.07
F	5.06	3.32	19.40	19.36	20.82	18.70	14.81	12.20	9.29	6.76
Si*	0.67	0.30	0.29	0.20	0.23	0.14	0.35	0.20	0.03	0.02
S	0.24	0.09	7.19	4.25	6.60	3.51	2.37	1.15	2.33	1.01
Zn	0.00	0.00	23.53	6.83	16.07	4.19	14.16	3.39	6.07	1.28

*Contamination from glass fibers

Fig. S13 Deconvoluted high-resolution N 1s spectra for the electrodes containing phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), 1-hydroxiphenazine (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN) after the charge and discharge steps (see inset for details). Experimental conditions: A Zn foil was used as the anode and 2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ served as the electrolyte. Separate electrodes were prepared for each half cycle.

Fig. S14 Calculated positions of the Zn²⁺ ion on the phenazine chemical structures. The substituents (R) represent different groups: -H for phenazine, -COOH for phenazine-1-carboxylic acid, -OH for phenazin-1-ol, and -CONH for phenazine-1-carboxamide.

Fig. S15 Deconvoluted high-resolution O 1s spectra for the electrodes containing phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), 1-hydroxiphenazine (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN) after the charge and discharge steps (see inset for details). Experimental conditions: A Zn foil was used as the anode and 2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ served as the electrolyte. Separate electrodes were prepared for each half cycle.

Fig. S16 Deconvoluted high-resolution Zn 2p_{3/2} spectra for the electrodes containing phenazine (PZ), phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA), 1-hydroxiphenazine (POH), and phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN) after the charge and discharge steps (see inset for details). Experimental conditions: A Zn foil was used as the anode and 2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ served as the electrolyte. Separate electrodes were prepared for each half cycle.

Table S3 Weighted mass for the FTIR measurements. specific capacitance derived from tests. and conversion percentage using 2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ as electrolyte

	Parameter	PZ	PCA	POH	PCN
Pristine ⁱ	<i>m</i> AM / mg	0.90	0.60	0.78	1.05
	<i>m</i> KBr / mg	139	123	154	152
After discharge to 1.4 V	<i>m</i> AM / mg	0.70	0.84	0.74	1.10
	<i>m</i> KBr / mg	133	144	150	155
After discharge to 0.3 V	<i>m</i> AM / mg	0.77	0.82	0.77	1.12
	<i>m</i> KBr / mg	138	135	152	155
<i>C</i> / mA hg ⁻¹	Charge	90	15	60	21
	Discharge	86	18	49	30
MW ⁱⁱ / g mol ⁻¹		180.21	224.21	196.20	223.23
<i>C</i> _{theor} ⁱⁱⁱ / mA h g ⁻¹		297.45	239.07	273.20	240.12
Conversion ^{iv} / %		29	7	18	13

AM = active material

ⁱ Powder obtained after preparing the working electrode, prior to any electrochemical treatment.

ⁱⁱ Molecular Weight of phenazine compounds.

ⁱⁱⁱ Theoretical specific capacitance calculated at a fully discharged state:

$$C_{theor} = \frac{1000nF}{3600MW}, \text{ where } n \text{ is the number of electrons (2), } F \text{ the Faraday constant (96485}$$

C mol⁻¹), and 3600 the conversion from seconds to hour.

^{iv} Specific capacitance obtained during the discharge step divided by the theoretical specific capacitance.

Fig. S17 *Ex situ* Fourier Transform Infrared spectra of the phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA) compound after use as the active material in the cathode of a Zn-ion battery under different conditions: pristine, after the charge step (1.4 V), and after the discharge step (0.3 V). Experimental conditions: the working electrode was prepared with PZ (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB, using **2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ as electrolyte**.

Fig. S18 *Ex situ* Fourier Transform Infrared spectra of the phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN) compound after use as the active material in the cathode of a Zn-ion battery under different conditions: pristine, after the charge step (1.4 V), and after the discharge step (0.3 V). Experimental conditions: the working electrode was prepared with PZ (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB, using **2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ as electrolyte**.

Table S4 Weighted mass for the FTIR measurements, specific capacitance derived from tests, and conversion percentage using 2 mol L⁻¹ Zn(OTf)₂ as electrolyte

	Parameter	PZ	PCA	POH	PCN
Pristine ⁱ	<i>m</i> AM / mg	0.90	0.90	0.75	0.63
	<i>m</i> KBr / mg	139	145	140	145
After discharge to 1.4 V	<i>m</i> AM / mg	0.90	0.60	0.90	0.65
	<i>m</i> KBr / mg	144	142	140	146
After discharge to 0.3 V	<i>m</i> AM / mg	0.95	1.05	1.05	0.55
	<i>m</i> KBr / mg	145	160	147	144
<i>C</i> / mA hg ⁻¹	Charge	94	66	71	45
	Discharge	83	58	79	45
MW ⁱⁱ / g mol ⁻¹		180.21	224.21	196.20	223.23
<i>C</i> _{theor} ⁱⁱⁱ / mA h g ⁻¹		297.45	239.07	273.20	240.12
Conversion ^{iv} / %		28	24	29	19

AM = active material

ⁱ Powder obtained after preparing the working electrode. prior to any electrochemical treatment.

ⁱⁱ Molecular Weight of phenazine compounds.

ⁱⁱⁱ Theoretical specific capacitance calculated at a fully discharged state:

$$C_{theor} = \frac{1000nF}{3600MW}, \text{ where } n \text{ is the number of electrons (2), } F \text{ the Faraday constant (96485}$$

C mol⁻¹), and 3600 the conversion from seconds to hour.

^{iv} Specific capacitance obtained during the discharge step divided by the theoretical specific capacitance.

Fig. S19 *Ex situ* Fourier Transform Infrared spectra of the phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA) compound after use as the active material in the cathode of a Zn-ion battery under different conditions: pristine, after the charge step (1.4 V), and after the discharge step (0.3 V). Experimental conditions: the working electrode was prepared with PZ (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB, using $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ Zn(OTf)}_2$ as electrolyte.

Fig. S20 *Ex situ* Fourier Transform Infrared spectra of the phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN) compound after use as the active material in the cathode of a Zn-ion battery under different conditions: pristine, after the charge step (1.4 V), and after the discharge step (0.3 V). Experimental conditions: the working electrode was prepared with PZ (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB, using $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ Zn(OTf)}_2$ as electrolyte.

Fig. S21 Color change of solutions containing POH at varying pH values and using K_2HPO_4 (from pH 1 to pH 7) or $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (from pH 8 to pH 12) at 10 mmol L^{-1} as buffer.

Fig. S22 a) Image of electrodes prepared with phenazine-1-ol (POH) as active material and PVDF as binder: *i)* after the charge step until 1.4 V vs Zn/Zn²⁺ and after discharge step until 0.3 V vs. Zn/Zn²⁺ and **b)** image of the glass fibers after the charge (*iii)* and discharge (*iv)*) steps using 2 mol L⁻¹ Zn(OTf)₂ as electrolyte. Experimental conditions: the working electrode was prepared with PZ (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB.

Fig. S23 Predicted vibrational spectra and experimental (*ex situ*) Fourier Transform Infrared spectra of phenazine (PZ) under different conditions: without (after the charge step at 1.4 V) and with Zn²⁺ ions (after the discharge step at 0.3 V). Experimental conditions: the working electrode was prepared with PZ (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB, using **2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ as electrolyte**.

Fig. S24 Predicted vibrational spectra and experimental (*ex situ*) Fourier Transform Infrared spectra of phenazine-1-carboxylic acid (PCA) under different conditions: without (after the charge step at 1.4 V) and with Zn^{2+} ions (after the discharge step at 0.3 V). Experimental conditions: the working electrode was prepared with PZ (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB, using **2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ as electrolyte**.

Fig. S25 Predicted vibrational spectra and experimental (*ex situ*) Fourier Transform Infrared spectra of phenazine-1-ol (POH) under different conditions: without (after the charge step at 1.4 V) and with Zn^{2+} ions (after the discharge step at 0.3 V). Experimental conditions: the working electrode was prepared with PZ (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB, using **2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ as electrolyte**.

Fig. S26 Predicted vibrational spectra and experimental (*ex situ*) Fourier Transform Infrared spectra of phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN) under different conditions: without (after the charge step at 1.4 V) and with Zn²⁺ ions (after the discharge step at 0.3 V). Experimental conditions: the working electrode was prepared with PZ (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB, using **2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ as electrolyte**.

Fig. S26 (continuation) Predicted vibrational spectra and experimental (*ex situ*) Fourier Transform Infrared spectra of phenazine-1-carboxamide (PCN) under different conditions: without (after the charge step at 1.4 V) and with Zn²⁺ ions (after the discharge step at 0.3 V). Experimental conditions: the working electrode was prepared with PZ (90% *m/m*) and PVDF solution in NMP (10% *m/m*), without KCB, using **2 mol L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ as electrolyte.**

Fig. S27 Cyclic voltammograms (2nd cycle at 10 mV s^{-1}) of a Zn/Zn cell using ZnSO_4 2 mol L^{-1} (black line), Zn(OTf)_2 2 mol L^{-1} (blue line), and Zn(OTf)_2 2 mol L^{-1} with PVA 50 g L^{-1} ($\text{Zn(OTf)}_2/\text{PVA}$: red line) as electrolytes. The arrows indicate the scan direction.

Fig. S28 Cell potential as a function of time (t) during stripping and plate experiments of a Zn/Zn cell using ZnSO_4 2 mol L^{-1} (black line), $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ 2 mol L^{-1} (blue line), and $\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2$ 2 mol L^{-1} with PVA 50 g L^{-1} ($\text{Zn}(\text{OTf})_2/\text{PVA}$: red line) as electrolytes. Experimental conditions: 0.5 mA cm^{-2} for 3600 s during oxidation and reduction steps.

Fig. S29 Logarithm of the electric current (I) as a function of applied potential (E – 1st scan) for a Zn electrode (0.096 cm² of exposed area) in distinct electrolytes: ZnSO₄ 2 mol L⁻¹ (black diamond), Zn(OTf)₂ 2 mol L⁻¹ (blue circle), and Zn(OTf)₂ 2 mol L⁻¹ with PVA 50 g L⁻¹ (Zn(OTf)₂/PVA: red triangle). Experimental conditions: 1 mV s⁻¹ and using a Pt foil as counter electrode.

Table S5 Current (I_{corr}) and potential (E_{corr}) of corrosion of Zn in distinct electrolytes

Electrolyte	$I_{\text{corr}} / \text{A}$	$E_{\text{corr}} / \text{V vs. Ag/AgCl/KCl (3 mol L}^{-1}\text{)}$
ZnSO ₄ 2 mol L ⁻¹	5.31×10^{-4}	-0.807
Zn(OTf) ₂ 2 mol L ⁻¹	7.55×10^{-6}	-0.800
Zn(OTf) ₂ 2 mol L ⁻¹ with PVA 50 g L ⁻¹	4.46×10^{-6}	-0.774

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